

Supplementary material - “I like using GenAI as a tool, but with the feeling that I’m better than it”: Exploring How Students Negotiate Computing Identity in the Age of GenAI

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Interview guide (translated from the original in Norwegian)

Introduction

Hello, my name is ... and I am writing my master’s thesis together with ... Thank you for taking the time to participate in this interview! We really appreciate you sharing your thoughts and experiences. This interview is part of our master’s thesis, in which we investigate how you, as an IT student, experience and use generative AI, and your thoughts on entering the workforce.

The interview will last approximately 30-60 minutes. There are no right or wrong answers. Please do not answer what you think we want to hear. We are only interested in your experiences and thoughts. If there is anything you do not wish to answer, you may skip it.

Your answers will be treated confidentially and anonymously. This means that no names or identifying information will be linked to this interview in our thesis. To ensure that we capture everything you say, we will record the interview. The recording will be used solely for analysis and will be deleted once the thesis is completed. You may withdraw at any time or request that we not use anything you have said.

Before we begin, we want to emphasize that when we say GenAI, we refer to generative AI tools that can generate text, code, or images based on input – for example, ChatGPT, Claude, Google Gemini, GitHub Copilot, Codeium, etc.

1. Before we get started, do you have any questions?

Getting to know the participant

2. Let’s start by you telling us a little about yourself and your background, such as what you study, what year you are in, and your IT experience, e.g., from work, volunteer positions, hobbies, etc.
3. Had you learn to program before you started your studies?
– What has been your experience learning to program?
4. During your studies, what have you learned the most from? For instance, the courses themselves, volunteer positions, work, or hobby projects?

5. Where will you start working this autumn?
 - Do you know if they use GenAI?

Relationship to GenAI tools

6. What is your relationship to GenAI tools?
 - How do you see it? A reference tool, a study assistant, or similar?
 - How enthusiastic are you about GenAI?
 - What about [the use of GenAI tools] in an academic context?
7. Has your relationship with GenAI tools changed from when you started using them until today?

Use of GenAI tools

8. How often do you use GenAI tools?
 - Where is the threshold for choosing to solve a task yourself versus letting a GenAI tool do it?
9. Which GenAI tools do you use, and for what purposes?
 - Why do you prefer these tools for those purposes?
 - What about in your studies?
10. How has GenAI affected the way you study?
 - How do you use GenAI to learn?
11. If you have a problem, how do you go about solving it?
12. Tell us about the last time you used a GenAI tool, or how you typically use one.
 - Can you give examples of prompts?
13. How comfortable are you using the GenAI tool?
 - When you prompt it, do you often have trouble getting it to do what you want?
 - Do you often have to correct it?

Attitudes towards GenAI tools

14. What advantages do using GenAI tools give you?
15. Have GenAI tools improved your ability to solve [complex] IT problems?
16. Do you have any concerns about your own use of GenAI tools?
 - What about in general?
 - What about your relationship to the ethical use of GenAI tools?
 - Why are these concerns problematic?

Job this autumn

17. Would you use the GenAI tool in [your job this autumn] in the same way you use it today?
18. Do you feel you have good insight into what is expected of you when you enter the workforce?
19. Do you feel there is a gap between what you have learned at university and what employers might expect?
20. Which skills do you feel confident in [now that you are about to enter working life]?
21. Which skills do you feel are underdeveloped or missing [now that you are about to enter working life]?

Thoughts about the future

22. How do you think GenAI tools have changed the business world? Have they shifted focus?
23. What do you think is more important today, or will become more critical in the future, because of GenAI tools? This can be anything from skills, competencies, and domains.
 - What has become or will become less important?

Conclusion

24. Before we finish, is there anything you want to say, something you feel was unclear, something you want to emphasize, or conclude with?

Thank you very much for taking the time to participate in this interview! We really appreciate it. We will now analyze all interviews to identify common themes and patterns. As mentioned, everything will be treated anonymously. If you have any questions afterward or wish to withdraw from the study, feel free to contact us.

Overview of the interview participants and the interview duration

The following table provides an overview of interview participants and the interview duration.

Table 1: Overview of the interview participants and the interview duration

ID	Study program at NTNU	Type of program	Specialization	Interview duration in minutes:seconds
S1	Informatics	2-year masters	Software systems	53:30
S2	Computer Science	5-year masters	Software systems	48:31
S3	Informatics	2-year masters	Software systems	67:05
S4	Computer Science	5-year masters	Software systems	46:11
S5	Computer Science	5-year masters	Software systems	46:18
S6	Computer Science	5-year masters	Databases and search	69:49
S7	Informatics	2-year masters	Software systems	74:27
S8	Computer Science	5-year masters	Artificial intelligence	69:54
S9	Computer Science	5-year masters	Algorithms and computer systems	48:06